

Dual Spin Statistics Prediction in Hadrons

Deep J. Dutta

Division of Nuclear Physics (DNP), American Physical Society, College Park, Maryland

Abstract

Few additional particles which possibly exist are pointed out here. The outcomes must be vindicated by experimental approaches in super energetic accelerators. The predicted particles are strongly interacting composite particles with “colored quarks” as its basic constituents.

Keywords: Standard Model, Coupling, CERN.

The standard model explains matter of about five percent in overall observable universe, the fact that something lies beyond the above mentioned statistics is clearly established by experiments but no interpretation have been proposed so far. The modification of standard model must lie in two objects first what are we observing and how do we explain them. The success of quantum Chromodynamics [1] in particle physics is overwhelming and precise (till date) verified by experiments. However as we mentioned “not everything”. We will propose some additional particles based on spin, our particles which we deduced are both fermions and bosons simply dual spin statistics predictions in Hadrons.

Idea of quarks [2] led us to formulate the new degree of freedom or simply quantum number “color charge” which was essentially needed to prevent the precise violation of exclusion principle [3]. The group $SU(3)$ is a gauge group contains three color charges, which means each of six flavors of quarks must possess three different color charges (6×3). QCD is based on this gauge group and its vector boson (gauge) is massless gluon. We will use such basic ideas to build the theoretical predictions discussed here. Quarks come in both types of electric

charges $+2/3$ and $-1/3$. based on our empirical calculations we therefore speculate that the newly calculated particle’s spin(s) are as follows: $+2, 0, 1, +5/2, -1/2, +1, +3, -1, 1, +7/2, -3/2, 1, 4, -2, 1$. Therefore one can observe that the outcomes indicates both Fermions and Bosons, simply dual statistics. However spin $+1/2, +3/2, 0, 1$ are observed by simply assuming that they are observed no matter what are they, but others of spin $+5/2, +3, +2, -2, +7/2, +4$ are not discovered hence we showed the existence (or at least speculated) of these particles theoretically. However for once and for all we need to experimentally demonstrate its concrete existence in large scale (energy) particle collider, perhaps CERN.

We do believe that this indication is a basic picture and needs more experimental work on this.

References

- [1] Politzer, H.D. (1974). “Asymptotic Freedom: An Approach to Strong Interaction”. Physics reports, 14
- [2] M. Gell-Mann, Phys. Letters 8, 214 (1964)
- [3] Nobel Lecture 1945, Wolfgang Pauli, Nobelprize.org